

NEW ASPECTS OF NITROGEN FIXATION AND CONSERVATION IN THE SOIL. PART II.

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Experiments have been made on soils after adding organic acids (both high and low carbon), oils like mahua, mustard and linseed and their effect on the fixation of nitrogen have been studied. Effects of canesugar, inulin, starch, cowdung and molasses in the nitrogen fixation in soil both in the artificial light and sunlight as well as in the dark have been investigated. Influence of temperature and light on nitrogen fixation has also been studied and the mechanism of nitrogen fixation with reference to energy change discussed.

We have discovered that sunlight or artificial light markedly increases nitrogen fixation in the soil mixed with energy materials like, carbohydrates, cellulose, fats, etc. Thus when 1 kg. of soil is mixed with definite weight of carbohydrates like canesugar, glucose etc. in basins and exposed to sunlight or artificial light daily for eight hours and another vessel containing the same material is kept in the dark, there is more nitrogen fixation in the vessels receiving light than in the dark.

The moisture is made up to 20% in the beginning to mix the ingredients properly. As there is considerable evaporation, more so in the light than in the dark, distilled water to the extent of 16% per cent. is added daily to the basins exposed to light and after three days in the basins kept in the dark, so as to keep a uniform moisture content. From time to time, the ammoniacal nitrogen, nitric nitrogen, total nitrogen and total carbon are estimated according to the modified Kjeldahl method of Robinson, McLean and Williams (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, 19, 315). The ammoniacal nitrogen was determined by treating 50 g. of the air-dried soil with 5 g. of pure potassium chloride and 5 g. of pure magnesium oxide and 100 c.c. of water and distilled for six hours upon a water-bath. A current of air, purified by passing through a solution of ferrous sulphate and sulphuric acid, was aspirated, and the ammonia produced was absorbed in dilute sulphuric acid and estimated colorimetrically by nesslerisation in a Duboscq colorimeter. The nitric nitrogen was estimated by treating the soil from which ammonia has been removed by the previous procedure with 1 g. of Devarda's alloy free from ammonia or nitrate and 25 c.c. or 1% sodium hydroxide solution and left overnight for the reduction of nitrite and nitrate to ammonia, which was estimated as in the previous case. The following are the experimental results.

Nitrogen Fixation with Organic Acids in Sunlight.

The soil (500 g.) was treated with 25 g. of pure acetic, oxalic, tartaric, citric, oleic, stearic, and palmitic acid. Very little fixation was observed with acetic and oxalic acids; with tartaric and citric acids, the increase in the total nitrogen of the soil was by a few mg. only, whereas with stearic, palmitic and oleic acids, a considerable amount of nitrogen fixation took place in one and half a year. Figures in the following tables indicate in mg. the amount of nitrogen fixed per 100 g. of soil.

TABLE I.

Stearic acid.

Started on 25-8-36.

$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	$\text{NO}_3\text{-N.}$	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
1.0	2.2	56.0	5152	4-9-36
1.2	2.0	56.0	5044	18-11-36
1.2	2.0	56.0	4923	9-1-37
0.6	2.2	55.4	3963.4	20-8-37
1.6	2.0	72.6	2572.5	24-1-38

Palmitic acid.

Started on 25-8-36.

1.0	2.2	56.0	6159	4-9-36
1.0	2.0	56.0	6145	18-11-36
1.2	2.0	58.0	6001	9-1-37
0.2	1.8	57.6	5864.2	20-8-37
1.2	1.8	66.7	2790	24-1-38

Oleic acid.

Started on 25-8-36.

1.0	2.2	56.0	5182.7	4-9-36
1.0	2.0	56.0	5086.7	18-11-36
1.3	2.1	56.0	5000	0-1-37
0.6	2.2	55.8	4123.4	20-8-37
1.4	1.7	63.6	1684.4	24-1-38

Nitrogen Fixation with Oils in Sunlight.

TABLE II.

500 G. soil + 50 g. linseed oil + 5 g. CaCO₃.

Started on 25-11-36.

NH ₅ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
1.2	1.6	58.3	6288	29-8-36
1.4	1.8	58.3	5991	11-9-36
1.4	1.8	58.3	5922	19-10-36
Traces	1.0	58.3	5912	7-1-37
Traces	0.6	58.3	5864	14-4-37
1.1	1.4	87.4	3530	15-1-38
500 G. soil + 50 g. mustard oil + 5 g. CaCO ₃ .				
1.4	1.8	51.1	6159	29-8-36
1.6	2.2	58.3	6000	11-9-36
1.6	2.2	58.3	6000	19-10-36
Traces	0.8	58.8	5981	7-1-37
Traces	0.6	58.8	5786	14-4-37
1.2	1.6	77.8	3900	15-1-38
500 G. soil + 50 g. mahua oil + 5 g. CaCO ₃ .				
1.2	1.6	63.6	6947	29-8-36
1.4	1.9	66.7	6428	11-9-36
1.4	1.9	66.7	6411	19-10-36
Traces	1.1	66.7	6412	7-1-37
Traces	0.6	66.7	6321	14-4-37
1.8	1.8	93.4	3600	15-1-38

Other energy materials have also been utilised (*cf. Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India, 1937, 3, 51, and Presidential address, Nat. Acad. Sci. India, 1937*).

We have also investigated the same phenomenon in artificial light. A 1,000 watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp was placed at a distance of 30 cm. above the basins containing the soil and energy materials. In these experiments the other conditions were the same as in the experiments in the sunlight. The following results have been obtained. Figures in the tables indicate the amount of nitrogen fixed in mg./100 g. soil.

Experiments in Artificial light with Canesugar.

TABLE III.

200 G. of soil + 2 g. of canesugar.

Started on 23-1-37.

Exposed to *light* for 8 hours daily.

NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
				original soil
1.6	2.4	45.1	499.8	4-2-37
1.7	2.4	48.2	650.5	3-3-37
2.6	2.4	54.4	544.0	3-3-37
2.4	2.5	60.9	418.5	12-4-37
2.6	2.6	59.2	418.7	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 33 mg.

Dark,

1.6	2.4	45.1	499.8	Original soil
1.5	2.4	45.1	739.3	4-2-37
1.4	2.4	46.6	636.1	3-3-37
1.7	2.4	48.2	401.7	12-4-37
2.4	2.6	48.2	401.7	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 6.2 mg.

200 G. of soil + 4 g. of canesugar.

Exposed to *light* for 8 hours daily.

1.6	2.4	45.1	499.8	Original soil
1.8	2.4	51.1	837.0	4-2-37
2.9	2.4	56.9	661.2	3-3-37
2.2	2.6	63.6	501.2	12-4-37
2.6	2.7	62.8	444.8	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 23 mg.

TABLE III (*contid.*).*Dark.*

NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
1·6	2·4	45·1	499·8	Original soil
1·6	2·4	46·7	979·2	4-2-37
1·3	2·4	46·6	712·4	3-3-37
1·6	2·4	51·1	401·7	12-4-37
2·6	2·6	50·1	401·7	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 6·8 mg.

200 G. soil + 6 g. canesugar.

Exposed to *light* for 8 hours daily.

1·6	2·4	45·1	499·8	Original soil
1·8	2·4	52·2	1021·1	4-2-37
3·0	2·4	58·3	736·5	3-3-37
2·5	2·8	66·7	527·3	12-4-37
2·6	2·8	65·1	454·8	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 20 mg.

Dark.

1·6	2·4	45·1	499·8	Original soil
1·6	2·4	47·6	143·9	4-2-37
1·0	2·4	48·2	837·0	13-3-37
1·6	2·4	52·3	401·7	12-4-37
2·6	2·6	51·8	401·7	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. carbon oxidised = 5·5 mg.

TABLE III (contd.).

200 G. soil + 10 g. canesugar.

Exposed to light for 8 hours daily.

NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
1.6	2.4	45.1	499.8	Original soil
1.8	2.4	51.1	1255.0	4-4-37
3.2	2.4	61.1	837.0	3-8-37
2.6	2.6	73.6	560.7	12-4-37
2.6	2.9	71.2	488.6	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 14 mg.

Dark.

1.6	2.4	45.1	499.8	Original soil
1.5	2.4	47.6	2098.0	4-2-37
1.0	2.0	50.0	1807.0	8-3-37
1.6	2.4	56.0	477.0	12-4-37
2.6	2.6	55.2	413.2	12-8-37

Nitrogen fixed per g. carbon oxidised = 5.4 mg.

Experiments in Artificial Light with Inulin.

TABLE IV.

Started on 2-9-37. 200 G. soil + 2 g. inulin. Exposed to light daily for 8 hours.

NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.0	1.5	46.7	621.4	18-9-37
1.6	1.6	47.8	611.0	18-10-37
1.2	1.5	58.6	456.5	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 30 mg.

TABLE IV (*contd.*).

$\text{NH}_4\text{-N.}$	$\text{NO}_3\text{-N.}$	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
<i>Dark.</i>				
0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.5	1.7	44.2	671.2	18-9-37
1.5	1.7	45.1	661.2	18-10-37
1.2	3.5	51.5	448.8	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 17 mg.

200 G. soil + 4 g. inulin. Exposed to *light* daily for 8 hours.

0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.2	2.1	48.3	887.2	18-9-37
2.0	1.9	49.3	686.3	18-10-37
3.5	2.0	68.2	568.1	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 27 mg.

Dark.

0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.6	1.8	45.1	877.4	18-9-37
1.8	1.8	46.8	711.2	18-10-37
1.8	1.3	63.6	652.4	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 24 mg.

200 G. soil + 6 g. inulin. Exposed to *light* daily for 8 hours.

0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.2	1.7	49.3	1915.1	18-9-37
2.4	1.7	51.2	1590.0	18-10-37
1.7	2.5	70.0	712.8	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 25 mg.

TABLE IV. (contd.).

Dark.

NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of sampling.
0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.6	1.8	46.2	1985.2	18-9-37
2.2	1.8	47.5	1315.0	18-10-37
1.6	1.2	64.8	719.8	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 20 mg.

200 G. soil + 10 g. inulin. Exposed to light daily for 8 hours.

0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.1	1.4	50.0	3296.0	18-9-37
2.8	1.6	52.0	2219.0	18-10-37
1.4	2.8	77.8	887.2	18-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 18 mg.

Dark.

0.9	3.5	43.7	460.3	Original soil
1.6	2.0	47.5	3232.0	18-9-37
1.6	1.8	48.2	1986.0	18-10-37
1.6	1.2	66.7	962.5	15-1-38

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 13 mg.

Influence of Temperature on Nitrogen Fixation.

In order to investigate the influence of temperature on nitrogen fixation in the dark, experiments were carried on in dishes in four replications placed in incubators kept in the dark at 20°, 30°, 35°, 40°, 45° and 50°. One set of basins was also exposed to sunlight to obtain comparable results in light. The following results have been obtained at different temperatures.

2% Glucose used in these experiments and the figures represent the amounts of total nitrogen in 100 g. of soil in mg.

TABLE V.

I.	II.	III.	IV	V.	VI.	VII.
20°	30°	40°	45°	50°	35°	Light
38·8	41·6	41·1	35·0	35·0	43·7	45·1 1
38·0	41·2	40·5	34·8	34·1	42·5	46·4 2
38·5	42·8	40·8	34·5	33·4	43·0	46·7 3
37·8	42·0	40·0	35·5	33·9	43·5	43·7 4

Original soil contained 33·7 mg. of total nitrogen.

The amount of nitrogen fixed in different cases.

I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	VII.	
20°	30°	40°	45°	50°	35°	Light	
5·1	7·9	7·4	1·3	1·3	10·0	11·4	
4·3	7·5	6·8	1·1	0·4	8·8	12·7	
4·8	9·1	7·1	0·8	0·3	9·3	13·0	
4·1	8·3	6·3	1·8	0·2	9·8	10·0	
Total	18·3	32·3	27·6	5·0	1·6	37·9	47·1
Mean	4·57	8·2	6·9	1·25	0·4	9·42	11·77

The above experiments show that the nitrogen fixation in the dark is highest at 35° and falls off with either increase or decrease of temperature. The nitrogen fixation in light, is, however, greater than the highest obtained in the dark.

Using completely sterile soil and mixing with energy materials nitrogen fixation has also been observed, 100 grams of ordinary garden soil were mixed with the requisite quantity of the energy material and distilled water and was placed in an autoclave in a silica or glass flask plugged with cotton wool for three to four hours for sterilising the mixture, which was then either exposed or kept in the dark. The following results have been obtained.

TABLE VI.

Exposed to sunlight from 8-5-37 to 15-7-37.

(Figures indicate in mg./100 g. of soil).

Condition.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	N fixed per g. of C oxidised.
Original soil	0.5	1.6	42.4	435.2	
anesugar 2% in a quartz flask	1.2	2.3	43.7	891.4	3.8 mg.
Canesugar 5% in a quartz flask	0.9	1.5	45.1	1740.9	4
Inulin 2% in a quartz boiling tube	1.1	1.7	48.3	444.1	5.9
Inulin 5% in a quartz boiling tube	1.0	2.1	49.8	1246.5	6.2
Starch 2% in a quartz flask	1.3	1.6	46.7	452.1	5.5
Starch 5% in a quartz flask	8.0	2.9	47.1	562.8	2.5

Dark.

The vessels were kept in the same place wrapped with black cloth.

Canesugar 2%	1.1	1.6	42.4	962.6	Nil
Canesugar 5%	0.9	1.6	42.4	1021.4	
Inulin 2%	0.9	1.6	43.7	535.6	1.4 mg.
Inulin 5%	0.7	1.6	42.1	1268.4	
Starch 2%	1.1	1.6	42.4	540.3	Nil
Starch 5%	0.6	1.6	42.4	987.6	

Exposed to sunlight from 25th Sept., 1937 to 2nd March, 1938.

Original soil			36.8	496.9	
Canesugar 2.5% in a 500 c.c. Jena conical flask			38.9	1240.4	4.1 mg.
Glucose 2.5% in a 500 c.c. Jena conical flask			39.8	1180.1	4.5

Dark.

Canesugar 2.5% in a 500 c.c. Jena conical flask wrapped with black cloth and kept by the side of the above flasks			37.2	1312.0	0.9
Glucose 2.5% in a 500 c.c. Jena conical flask as above			37.8	1258.0	2.0

The foregoing results show that under comparable conditions, the amount of nitrogen fixed per gram of carbon oxidised is always much greater in light than in the dark. Moreover our experimental results show definitely that the increased nitrogen fixation observed in the light is not due to increase of temperature when the mixture is exposed to light. It has been observed that the optimum temperature for nitrogen fixation is 35° in the dark; when the temperature is increased or decreased, the nitrogen fixation becomes less. The temperature of the basins receiving sunlight or artificial light is appreciably higher than the optimum although the fixation in light is always greater than even at the optimum temperature in the dark. Another remarkable behaviour is also observed that although azotobacter numbers in the exposed dishes or in fields is much smaller than in the covered ones, the amounts of nitrogen fixed are always greater in light than in the dark (*cf.* Presidential Address National Acad. Sci. India, Jan. 1937). In the basin experiments, the azotobacter in the soils kept in the dark are approximately ten times greater in the dark than in the sunlight, but the nitrogen fixation in basin kept in light is more than double than in those kept in the dark. In the field trials, also the same behaviour is observed, although the azotobacter numbers are smaller in the plots receiving sunshine than in the covered ones, the nitrogen fixation is also double in light than in the dark. In experiments completely anaerobic conditions are maintained by stirring the soil and if nitrogen fixation in the soil is entirely a bacterial process, the nitrogen fixation should have been proportional to the azotobacter numbers, but it is otherwise.

We have repeatedly observed that the maximum error possible in our basin experiments in the estimation of total nitrogen never exceeds 1%. In the field trials, difference in sampling causes a variation of about 3% in the total nitrogen. It is quite clear, therefore, that the largely increased nitrogen fixation observed either in sunlight or in artificial light cannot be ascribed to experimental error.

Moreover, the experimental results recorded with sterile soil show that there is an appreciable amount of nitrogen fixation even in the complete absence of bacteria. This is a new finding to which we attach great importance because nitrogen fixation has been ascribed so far to the growth of micro-organisms but our experiments show that these agents are not absolutely necessary.

Our results show that in no case even in the presence of cowdung and hay containing appreciable amounts of nitrogen in the beginning, the oxidation of carbon in the dark is greater than in light, although the

microbial population is greater in the dark than in light. It has been stated by soil bacteriologists that the velocity of the decomposition of carbohydrates and cellulose materials depends on the presence of available nitrogen in the system. The available nitrogen is believed to supply the need of the micro-organisms to build their tissues and the food is supplied by the energy materials. It is believed, therefore, that the decomposition of the energy materials is thus facilitated by the increase of the microbial population. In light, however, no such behaviour is observed, because the velocity of the cellulose or carbohydrate oxidation and the nitrogen fixation in light is greater than that in the dark. It is clear, therefore, that light plays a prominent part in the oxidation of energy materials and nitrogen fixation in the soil.

In order to investigate the maximum amounts of nitrogen fixation possible on the application of molasses to soil the following experiments were performed. Figures in the following tables indicate the amount of nitrogen fixed in mg. per 100 g. of soil.

TABLE VII.

500 G. of soil+125 g. of molasses.				
Started on 31-8-36.				
	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil	1'4	2'4	56'0.	606'7
19-10-36	3'5	4'6	140'0	3348'0
6-1-37	2'1	5'8	149'9	2511
17-3-37	1'8	5'9	116'7	4199
28-8-37	1'9	10'4	78'6	1386
15-1-38	1'8	2'5	87'5	937'3
500 G. of soil+125 g. of molasses+25 g. of CaCO ₃ .				
Original soil	1'4	2'4	56'0	606'7
19-10-36	1'8	3'7	100'0.	2080
6-1-37	1'9	3'7	91'2	1674
17-3-37	2'5	3'7	87'5	1127
28-8-37	2'2	6'4	61'2	986'6
15-1-38	1'5	2'1	75'0	700'2

TABLE VIII.

Fixation with cowdung alone.

Started on 16-2-37.

	<i>Light.</i>		<i>Dark.</i>	
	Total N.	Total C.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil	2000	39300	2000'0	39300
20-4-37	1783'6	38500	1986'0	37340
26-8-37	2410'0	34500	2000'0	38400
7-2-38	2169'0	26700	2000'0	30410
14-5-38	2156'0	25840	2000'0	28450

Transfer of Energy from one Chemical change to another and the Mechanism of Nitrogen Fixation.

For over twenty-five years in numerous publications from this laboratory, we have been investigating the initiation of exothermal reactions by the energy obtained from another exothermal reaction. Thus we have shown that the energy derived from the oxidation of an aqueous solution of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate, can form a large amount of calomel from a mixture of mercuric chloride and oxalic acid even in the dark. Moreover, the oxidation of sodium sulphite or ferrous hydroxide or cerous hydroxide or manganous hydroxide by air leads to the oxidation of nickelous hydroxide or carbohydrates, fats, proteins, etc., even in the absence of light. The energy materials like carbohydrates, fats and proteins have also been oxidised simply by passing air through their solutions or suspensions exposed to light. In all these, exothermic reactions have been initiated either through the agency of light or the energy available from another exothermal chemical reaction.

Our results show that nitrogen fixation in sunlight or artificial light is much greater than that obtained in the dark per gram of the energy material oxidised. As the amount of energy available from the oxidation of one gram of energy material is the same, both in the light and the dark, it is

expected that the nitrogen fixation should be the same in light as in the dark, but the experimental results show that with all the energy materials, the nitrogen fixation for the same amount of energy output from the oxidation of the energy material, in light is much greater than in the dark. Hence we are led to conclude that in nitrogen fixation, which is an endothermal reaction, the radiations of the sun or other sources are actually utilised in effecting more nitrogen fixation as in photosynthesis or carbon assimilation in plants or in the formation of ozone by light absorption.

From the foregoing observations it is clear that nitrogen fixation can take place in the dark when the soil is supplied with energy obtained from the oxidation of energy materials, like carbohydrates, pentosans, cellulose, oils, fats, etc., but the nitrogen fixation is considerably increased when these systems also receive sunlight or artificial light, which is utilised in this process as in photosynthesis in the plant kingdom or in the formation of ozone by light absorption.

Recent experiments of Dhar and Seshacharyulu show that the nitrogen fixation in soil fed with 2% glucose in the dark is 7.76 mg., whereas 13.1 mg. of nitrogen are fixed in light per gram of carbon oxidised at a temperature of 42°. Hence light and not increase of temperature is responsible for increased nitrogen fixation in light.

Dhar and Atma Ram have shown that the amount of formaldehyde formed by exposing potassium bicarbonate solutions to sunlight in quartz vessels is smaller than the amount formed in the photo-oxidation of organic substances. Moreover, when we compare the amounts of formaldehyde formed with the number of molecules of bicarbonate decomposed or the organic substance oxidised, a great difference is at once observed. Although the salts of the fatty acids are oxidised to a smaller extent than the carbohydrates and the amino-acids under comparable conditions, the amount of formaldehyde produced is greater in the case of the salts of the fatty acids than with carbohydrates and amino-acids.

It is well known that large amounts of energy are liberated in the oxidation of carbohydrates

This energy can be utilised in bringing about the endothermal reaction between nitrogen and oxygen ($N_2 + O_2 + 432 \text{ Cal } 2NO$) on the soil surface even in the absence of sunlight. The oxide of nitrogen in contact with the

soil moisture and lime can cause the formation of the calcium nitrite and nitrate, which may be reduced to ammonium salts by the excess of carbohydrates added to the soil. Moreover, the energy liberated in the oxidation of carbohydrates on the soil surface may lead to the decomposition of water molecules according to the following equation

The atomic hydrogen can readily combine with molecular nitrogen forming ammonium salts on the soil surface. When soil, mixed with carbohydrates, glycerol, etc., comes in contact with air, the carbon decreases and the total and the ammoniacal nitrogen increases by nitrogen fixation. By light absorption, all these processes, which can take place in the dark provided the energy of the oxidation of the carbohydrates is available on the soil surface, are accelerated and hence more nitrogen fixation per gram of the energy material oxidised is observed in light. Under natural conditions large amounts of nitrogen are fixed in the soil with the energy of the oxidation of cellulose aided by sunlight and this is a phenomenon of great importance to plant life.

According to Moore (1921), sunlight causes a slight union of nitrogen and oxygen in the air resulting in the formation of oxides of nitrogen. Dhar and Sanyal (1925) have observed the formation of traces of nitrous acid when air, freed from impurities, is bubbled through conductivity water in presence of ultraviolet light. This reaction cannot go far, as nitrous acid decomposes readily in light according to the equation

Moreover, nitric acid and nitrates also decompose in light. Similarly the following reaction

can take place to a very limited extent in air as formaldehyde readily decomposes in light. Dhar and Atma Ram obtained 0.007 g. formaldehyde per litre of freshly collected rain water. The combination of nitrogen and oxygen and carbon dioxide and water vapour are greatly accelerated when, along with sunlight, the energy of carbohydrate oxidation is available to the system.

Berthelot (*Compt. rend.*, 1900, 130, 1345, 1430, 1662) has reported the formation of small quantities of nitric acid in the oxidation of substances like carbon, sulphur, metals and hydrogen especially in his calorimetric bombs. At the ordinary pressure even less than 1 mg. of nitric acid is formed with a mixture of nitrogen and oxygen in the oxidation of amorphous carbon. With air the yield of nitric acid is one tenth (Russell, *J. Chem.*

Soc., 1903, 83, 1263) obtained small quantities of ammonium of nitrite and nitrate in the oxidation of phosphorus by oxygen. It appears that the energy of oxidation can be utilised in nitrogen fixation.

The efficiency of nitrogen fixation is also as low as in the case of carbon assimilation. It is well known that in many cases, only 0.1 to 0.2% of the light energy is utilised in carbon assimilation in plants. In our experiments with nitrogen fixation, not even 1% of the energy liberated by the oxidation of the carbohydrates or cellulosic materials is utilised in nitrogen fixation.

As the soil is porous and the surface is renewed in cultivation, the influence of light can be effective in the soil brought under cultivation. Moreover, the light penetration in soils under tropical conditions is likely to be important.

It is well known that nitrogen is an elusive substance and as much as 60% of the added nitrogenous compound used as manure is lost as gaseous nitrogen from the soil in the course of their oxidation. Hence the nitrogenous compounds formed by fixation are also oxidised on the soil surface and undergo loss due to the formation and decomposition of the unstable substance, ammonium nitrite produced in the course of the oxidation of the proteins, ammonium salts and other nitrogenous compounds. The whole of the nitrogen fixed in soil cannot remain there for a long time because of this loss.

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Received September 27, 1938.
